

Photoelectrochemical generation of H₂O₂ using hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) and gas diffusion electrode (GDE)

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Abstract

In contrast to the industrial-scale production of H₂O₂ the electrochemical or photoelectrochemical synthesis is environmentally friendly. In the present work, the photoelectrochemical generation of H₂O₂ was studied by combining the hematite (α -Fe₂O₃/FTO/glass) photoanode and gas diffusion electrode (GDE) modified by incorporation of tin (II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) in its hydrophilic layer. The experiments were carried out in a photoelectrochemical cell with two compartments separated by a proton exchange membrane under applied bias and AM1.5 irradiation (100 mW/cm²). The generated amount of H₂O₂ was determined by chemical analysis (visible light spectrophotometry) of the electrolyte. As a tool to determine the efficiency of such a process, the Faradaic efficiency (*FE*) was calculated. The best configuration used air as an inlet gas for GDE and phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) as an electrolyte in the cathodic compartment. The combination of hematite and GDE (with SnPc) was the most effective in H₂O₂ photoelectrochemical generation. The highest value of *FE* was 52.4 % for GDE (O₂ reduction to H₂O₂) and 0.4 % for hematite photoanode (H₂O oxidation to H₂O₂).

Keywords: hematite, GDE, H₂O₂ generation, Faradaic efficiency

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1 Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) finds extensive applications across various industrial sectors, with a significant presence in both the chemical industry and environmental protection efforts. Its utilisation results in the water as a byproduct, significantly contributing to eco-friendly ways within the chemical industry. The industrial-scale production of hydrogen peroxide primarily relies on the anthraquinone oxidation (AO) process catalysed by the rare metal palladium (Pd) as shown in eq. 1.

However, due to its inherent drawbacks, the AO process cannot be considered environmentally friendly. This process encompasses a series of steps involving the hydrogenation and oxidation of an alkylanthraquinone precursor, which is dissolved in a mixture of harmful organic solvents. Subsequently, liquid-liquid extraction is employed to recover the hydrogen peroxide. These aspects adversely impact both its sustainability and production costs. Furthermore, the transportation, storage, and handling of bulk quantities of hydrogen peroxide pose risks and result in escalating expenses [1]. As a result, researchers are actively exploring innovative and more environmentally friendly methods to produce hydrogen peroxide. One of the promising alternatives to the AO method is the photoelectrochemical (PEC) production of hydrogen peroxide which can be performed *via* two processes. The first one is the oxygen (O_2) reduction reaction (ORR), the second is the water oxidation reaction (WOR).

While numerous studies have been focused on the generation of H_2O_2 through the ORR (eq. 2) [2-5], comparatively less emphasis has been placed on the WOR for H_2O_2 production [6] (e.g. on TiO_2 [7], BiVO_4 [7] or WO_3 [8]) (eq. 3). Being the reverse process of the ORR, the WOR also entails a multielectron mechanism. In photoelectrochemical water oxidation reactions, the evolution of H_2O_2 (eq. 3) is thermodynamically less favourable compared to O_2 evolution (eq. 4) ($E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} - E_{\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.547 \text{ V}$). But sluggish reaction kinetics necessitate an overpotential exceeding $\eta > 400 \text{ mV}$ for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER, eq. 4). This high overpotential for triggering the OER opens up the possibility of initiating H_2O_2 production during the multielectron transfer process *via* WOR (eq. 3).

An electrochemical or photoelectrochemical system utilized for the production of only H_2O_2 could be designed based on a two-electron process (eq. 5) or a four-electron process (eq. 6). The four-electron process requires twice the amount of charge to produce the same amount of H_2O_2 as in the two-electron process.

Due to this fact, there are still great efforts to improve the (photo)electrochemical production of H_2O_2 through the two-electron process. Recently, photoelectrochemical production of H_2O_2 *via* ORR was studied in a system combining BiVO_4 as a photoanode and a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) as a cathode [9]. The present work is based on a similar approach, but employing hematite as a photoanode.

Hematite is currently an extensively studied n-type semiconductor with the possibility of its use as a photoanode in various photoelectrochemical applications [10-12]. The most widespread application of hematite-based photoanodes (see Fig. S1b) is light-assisted water electrolysis (alternatively PEC water splitting). However, hematite has also found use in other photooxidation processes which are starting to gain attention, namely (i) the photoelectrochemical oxidation (degradation) of organic impurities in water (e.g. salicylic acid or acid orange 7) as a part of environmental protection efforts [13-16] and (ii) the photoelectrochemical oxidation of inorganic ions (e.g. bromide anions) in aqueous solutions [17, 18]. Hematite in the form of photoanode can be prepared by various deposition techniques such as magnetron sputtering [19], hydrothermal synthesis [20], electrochemical deposition [21] or spray pyrolysis (SP) [22]. The SP technique is often used mainly for its wide versatility (possible setting of deposition temperature, spray flow rate, fineness of spray adjusting the excess pressure etc.) and the possibility of spraying dimensionally larger substrates. The possibility of simple scale-up brings spray pyrolysis significantly closer to eventual use in potential practical applications. The main advantage of hematite is the possibility of its use in the visible part of the solar spectrum ($E_g = 2.1 \text{ eV}$, $\lambda_{\text{onset}} = 590 \text{ nm}$) [23], compared to titanium

dioxide ($E_g = 3.2$ eV, $\lambda_{\text{onset}} = 388$ nm) [24]. However, hematite suffers from some disadvantages such as low majority carrier mobility [25] or instability in an acidic environment ($\text{pH} \leq 2$) [26]. The first shortcoming is typically overcome by doping with elements such as Sn [23, 27] and Ti [22, 28]. In the case of hematite instability at lower pHs, even at $\text{pH} < 2$ (0.01 M H_2SO_4) the dissolution rate of hematite was found very low (decrease 0.171 nm/day) [22], and can be even further decreased by the coverage with protective overlayers like TiO_2 [29, 30] or SnO_2 [31, 32]. This contributes to the significant advantage of hematite over BiVO_4 , which is typically used only in the neutral pH (mainly buffers) due to its poor chemical and photoelectrochemical stability [33].

A gas diffusion electrode (GDE, see Fig. S1c) offers a solution to overcome the mass transport limitations commonly encountered in classic H-type cells with conventional metal plates or granular electrodes due to its high porosity, operating current densities, and partial hydrophobicity [34] (see Fig. S1e and f). The three-phase interface of the gas-solid-liquid characteristic of GDEs facilitates the uniform distribution of reactants and intermediate products across the catalyst surface, making them particularly advantageous for O_2 reduction originating from air at the liquid-gas phase boundary. Furthermore, the three-phase nature of GDEs aids in separating liquid and gaseous products during the ORR.

Efficient catalyst development for integration into GDEs is crucial to minimize the overpotential for ORR. Metal phthalocyanine (MPC) is a thermally and chemically stable molecule with a flat structure as shown in Fig. S1d. It has a metal-N₄ structure, in which a single metal atom (e.g. Sn, Co or Ni) is coordinated to four nitrogen atoms in the molecule, and is one of the monoatomic catalysts with metal atoms as active sites. By adding MPC to GDE, it is possible to expect an increase in activity due to electron accumulation in the central metal cation and an improvement in selectivity due to a change of the mentioned cation. Such changes in reactivity and selectivity are mainly caused by the difference in binding energies between the reaction site and reactants or intermediate products [35, 36]. The reaction mechanism of O_2 reduction on a catalyst can be either an associative mechanism, in which the O=O bond is not cleaved after O_2 adsorption, or a dissociative mechanism, in which the O=O bond is cleaved. In the associative mechanism, the activity increases with the adsorption of O_2 molecules and OOH^* . The adsorption energy of the second O^* step also affects the selectivity, and the lower the adsorption energy, the higher the selectivity of the two-electron reduction reaction is expected to be. One of the possible reasons for the change in adsorption energy is the effect of the d-electron number of the central metal: in the case of O_2 reduction, the increase in d-

electrons leads to an antibonding state of the metal-oxygen bond, destabilizing the O* intermediate and improving selectivity [35].

In this study, we combined for the first time α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode with an SnPc-modified GDE (for an illustrative image see Fig. S1). Firstly, to see whether the hematite can produce H₂O₂ in HCO₃⁻ containing electrolyte *via* WOR. Secondly, to determine the beneficial role of α -Fe₂O₃ photopotential on the ability of GDE (with or without SnPc) to generate H₂O₂ through ORR. The efficiency of the described photoelectrochemical processes (H₂O₂ production either *via* WOR or ORR) was determined by calculations of Faradaic efficiencies (*FE*).

2 Experimental

2.1 Chemicals, electrode preparation, H₂O₂ analysis

Chemicals, deposition and characterisation of hematite films, GDE preparation and measurements of H₂O₂ concentration are described in detail in Supplementary Information (chapters S1.1, S1.2, S1.3 and S1.4).

2.2 Photoelectrochemical characterization

The photoelectrochemical cell was equipped with a fused silica window. Counter and reference electrodes were in a compartment separated from the working electrode by a proton exchange membrane. Experiments were carried out in two electrode setup (GDE *vs.* counter electrode), only when the distribution of applied bias on α -Fe₂O₃ and GDE was measured, the Ag/AgCl reference electrode was used. As a cathode gas diffusion electrode (GDE) was used. The GDE was immersed in 30 ml of 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) or 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7.2). Catholyte was bubbled with air or argon, respectively. In the case of argon, pre-bubbling before the experiment was done with a duration of 30 min. The anodic compartment contained hematite as a photoanode and 40 ml of 1 M potassium hydrogen carbonate (KHCO₃). Anolyte was bubbled with CO₂ to maintain the pH value of the KHCO₃ solution. pH was measured by a pH meter (Horiba Co. Ltd., F-74S, Japan). Pre-bubbling took 30 min. Measurements were performed using Hokudo Denko Co. Ltd. HSV-110 (Japan) potentiostat. In the case of measurements with a reference electrode (3 M chloride, $E_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}} = 0.210$ V *vs.* NHE) the multimeter (Kyoritsu Corp., Japan) was used. Voltammetry and chronoamperometry were carried out under the front side irradiation. As a light source, a solar simulator (Pecell

Technologies Co. Ltd. PEC-L15, 150 W Xe arc lamp, Japan) with AM1.5G filter, irradiance 1 sun (100 mW/cm²) was used.

2.3 PEC performance of α -Fe₂O₃ and GDE

The PEC performance of hematite or GDE in the studied photoelectrochemical system was evaluated by calculation of the Faradaic efficiency (*FE*). The *FE* for ORR and WOR was calculated from the ratio of the electric current required for the formation of a product to the total electric current passed through the PEC system during the experiment period (eq. 7)

$$FE (\%) = \frac{z_{e^-} \cdot F \cdot r(X)}{i} \cdot 100 \% \quad (7)$$

where z_{e^-} is the number of electrons required for the formation of the product X, F is the Faraday constant (96 485 C/mol), $r(X)$ is the formation rate of the product (X) in mol/s and i is the (photo)current measured during the time of the experiment.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Physical characterization of α -Fe₂O₃ thin films and GDE

Based on the previous work [22], Ti doped hematite films of optimised thickness (around 200 nm) on FTO/glass were fabricated by spray pyrolysis and characterised by XRD and Scanning Electron Microscopy (see S1.2). As shown in Fig.S2, we deposited phase pure hematite without evidence of any other iron oxides (e.g. FeO (wüstite) or Fe₃O₄ (magnetite)) that can negatively influence the photoelectrochemical performance. The evidence of SnO₂ (cassiterite) is due to the selected substrate (FTO/glass). The top view SEM morphology of hematite layers is shown in Fig.S3. We can see nicely connected particles of hematite with some sharp edges confirming good crystallinity as proven by XRD. GDE on nickel mesh was prepared in the same way as in our previous work [9, 37] (see S1.3). The photograph of GDE with good mechanical stability can be seen in Fig S1c. The diameter of the GDE was 20 mm.

3.2 Oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) on GDE

To investigate the electrochemical properties of the O_2 reduction reaction at the interface of a gas diffusion electrode modified with a tin (II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) catalyst, the linear sweep voltammetry ($i-E$) and chronoamperometry ($j-t$) measurements in two electrode configuration were performed. Fig. 1 shows the $i-\Delta E$ curves for GDE without and with incorporating SnPc in the hydrophilic layer using two inlet gases, namely air and argon. As expected there was a significant shift in the current onset potential when the inlet gas was changed from Ar to air (approximately 400 mV). This confirms that the ORR start to take place at less negative potentials than the hydrogen evolution reaction. The presence of SnPc resulted in the positive shift of onset potential for ORR (approximately 100 mV). It could be ascribed to the beneficial role of SnPc in the hydrophilic part of GDE due to its unique properties.

Fig. 1 $i-\Delta E$ curves of GDE (no SnPc) vs. $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ with air as inlet gas (blue curve, circles) and GDE (with SnPc) vs. $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ with argon (black curve, squares) or air (blue curve, triangles) as inlet gases. As a catholyte 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M $KHCO_3$ (pH 7.7) were used. The irradiated area of the $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ photoanode was 1.5 cm^2 (irradiation 100 mW/cm^2 (1 sun)).

Fig. S3 shows the potential of GDE (SnPc) cathode and $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$ photoanode under light irradiation at various applied biases (ΔE) ranging from 0 to -1.8 V (GDE vs. $\alpha-Fe_2O_3$). Up to applied bias -1 V , both potentials increase linearly. The voltage distribution across both electrodes under light irradiation is asymmetric for higher bias values. The higher increase in

the potential of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanode compared to the GDE (SnPc) suggests an up-trend in resistivity at the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ photoanode under larger applied biases.

3.2.1 Influence of SnPc

To further investigate and confirm the positive effect of SnPc presence in the hydrophilic layer of the gas diffusion electrode on the selectivity for ORR, chronoamperometry at bias -1 V (GDE vs. $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) was conducted (Fig. 2a). The H_2O_2 concentration (see S1.4) was measured after 1, 3, and 5 hours of polarization (for each time one experiment) and based on the measured values, Faradaic efficiency was calculated (eq. 7). As depicted in Fig. 2, the presence of SnPc in the GDE had a beneficial impact on H_2O_2 generation *via* ORR. This presence led to higher values of generated hydrogen peroxide over time. Fig. 2b shows that the H_2O_2 concentration increased almost linearly and was about 2 times higher compared to the GDE without SnPc modification. This results in Faradaic efficiencies of around 50 % for GDE with SnPc modification while GDE without SnPc only reached about 30 % of *FE* over time. Values of Faradaic efficiencies proved that the selectivity for ORR reaction by incorporating SnPc as a catalyst was significantly enhanced.

Fig. 2 a) j - t curves for GDE without SnPc (black curve) and GDE with SnPc (blue curve) with $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ as a counter electrode, b) measured concentrations of H_2O_2 in μM (red curves, without SnPc – squares, with SnPc – circles) and calculated Faradaic efficiencies in % after 1, 3 and 5 hours (black curves, without SnPc – squares, with SnPc – circles). Air was used as an inlet gas for GDE. As a catholyte, 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH

7.4) bubbled with CO₂ were used. Irradiation 100 mW/cm² (1 sun). Applied bias -1 V (GDE vs. α-Fe₂O₃).

3.2.2 Influence of catholyte

The positive effect of GDE modification with SnPc was compared in two electrolytes in the cathodic compartment, namely 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7.2). As a photoanode, hematite in 1 M KHCO₃ anolyte was used. As shown in Fig. S5a the steady value of photocurrent around -0.4 mA/cm² was measured over time interval (5 hours). The concentration of H₂O₂ after 5 hours was 713 μM, which was approximately half of that found for the cell with the same configuration and 0.5 M phosphate buffer as a catholyte. The positive influence of the phosphate buffer on the performance of the GDE in the studied PEC system was confirmed by the calculation of the Faradaic efficiency, which for the phosphate buffer was more than two times higher than for Na₂SO₄ solution (52 % vs. 24 %) (see Figs. 2b and S5b). This result is in agreement with the previous work of Shiraishi et al. [38] who found that at high concentrations of H₂O₂ synthesised in photoelectrochemical systems, disproportionation reactions and H₂O₂ decomposition take place. Therefore, hydrogen peroxide was stabilized by phosphate ion (H₂PO₄⁻) to suppress these decomposition reactions. In simplicity, phosphate ions associate with H₂O₂ *via* hydrogen bonds to form stable complexes, inhibiting the decomposition reaction of H₂O₂ to water and oxygen.

3.2.3 Hematite as a counter electrode (comparison with Pt)

Production of H₂O₂ *via* ORR on GDE was compared for two counter electrodes (CE), platinum (electrochemical (EC) process) and hematite (photoelectrochemical (PEC) process). We can see in Fig. 3 that in the case of hematite as CE the onset for the ORR was significantly shifted in a favourable direction by up to 400 mV compared with Pt. A more favourable onset position for ORR in the case of hematite as CE can be attributed to the positive effect of the semiconductor's photopotential, which significantly favours the PEC process.

Fig. 3 i - ΔE curves of GDE (with SnPc) vs. counter electrodes (CE): (i) $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (black squares) and (ii) Pt (blue circles). Air was used as inlet gases for GDE. As a catholyte 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH 7.7) were used. The active area of the platinum anode was 1.5 cm^2 . The same hematite area was irradiated with AM1.5 (100 mW/cm^2).

To see the influence of the counter electrode on H_2O_2 production, chronoamperometry was performed for 5 hours with Pt. As shown in Fig. S6, use of Pt resulted in lower photocurrent (-0.2 mA/cm^2) than in the case of hematite (Fig. 2a). It is worth mentioning that in the case of hematite, H_2O_2 concentration after 1 h reached 5.6 times higher value and after 5 h approximately 18.7 times higher value than in the case of Pt as CE (increase from 37 to 206 μM and from 73 to 1260 μM , respectively). The same trend could be observed for Faradaic efficiencies as the current for Pt was steady, but the H_2O_2 evolution in time did not follow a linear increase (Fig. 4). As a result there is a significant difference in Faradaic efficiencies over time (12.8 vs. 49.5 % after 1 h and 4.5 vs. 52.4 % after 5 h). In the case of Pt as CE, the charge was used for the ORR reaction significantly less efficiently than in the system consisting of GDE and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ as a photoanode (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 4 The measured concentration of H₂O₂ (red) in μM and calculated Faradaic efficiencies (black) in % after 1, 3 and 5 hours for GDE (with SnPc) vs. counter electrodes (CE): (i) α-Fe₂O₃ (squares) and (ii) Pt (circles). Air was used as an inlet gas for GDE. As a catholyte, 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO₃ (pH 7.7) bubbled with CO₂ were used. Applied bias -1 V (GDE vs. α-Fe₂O₃).

3.3 H₂O₂ generation by water oxidation (WOR)

As mentioned, the evolution of H₂O₂ is thermodynamically less favourable compared to O₂ evolution ($E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} - E_{\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.547 \text{ V}$). Thus, the practical implementation of photoelectrochemical WOR for H₂O₂ evolution remains largely unexplored. The decrease in reaction selectivity of the H₂O₂ synthesis *via* the WOR (eq. 3) due to competition with the OER (eq. 4) can be improved by the selection of an electrolyte solution. Fuku et al. reported [39] that the selectivity of H₂O₂ synthesis in the OER on tungsten trioxide/bismuth vanadate photoanode was dramatically improved by using a solution containing HCO₃⁻ as the electrolyte. HCO₃⁻ in solution adsorbs on the anode surface and forms HCO₄⁻ and C₂O₆²⁻ percarbonate species in the oxidation reaction. As an example, the formation of HCO₄⁻ proceeds according to eq. 8 [40]. Subsequent hydrolysis of the percarbonate species produces H₂O₂ and HCO₃⁻ (eq. 9).

Bubbling of CO₂ gas into the electrolyte solution can also increase H₂O₂ production. The increasing dissolved amount of CO₂ causes an increase in the concentration of HCO₃⁻ and a decrease in pH, based on the following equilibrium equations (eqs. S1-S3 in SI). The measurements of H₂O₂ concentrations were performed in the anolyte solution (1 M KHCO₃) where the hematite photoanode was placed. Measurements were performed by combining hematite photoanode and GDE with SnPc (the most efficient configuration considering *FE*, see Fig. 2b). As the 1 M KHCO₃ solution used in this study is slightly alkaline (pH 8.4), the decomposition of H₂O₂ is suppressed by the decrease in pH due to CO₂ bubbling (pH 7.7). H₂O₂ was detected only after 5 hours, the concentration was approximately 0.05 mg/l (15 μM) which corresponds to an almost negligible value of *FE* (0.4 %). Similarly, low values of H₂O₂ concentrations were found by Chao et al. [9] on WO₃ (14 μM) and BiVO₄ (5.5 μM) photoanodes in combination with GDE.

3.4 Comparison of ORR and WOR for H₂O₂ production

As described above and shown in Table S1, the highest values of H₂O₂ concentrations were found for the configuration of hematite photoanode and GDE (with SnPc) as cathode using the 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) as a catholyte and air as an inlet gas for GDE. The Faradaic efficiency was 52.4 % after 5 hours resulting in 1 260 μM of H₂O₂ in the electrolyte solution on the GDE side. For this most efficient combination, the concentration of H₂O₂ on the α-Fe₂O₃ side (anolyte 1 M KHCO₃ (pH 7.7) bubbled with CO₂ to maintain the pH) was only 0.4 % corresponding to approximately 15 μM of H₂O₂ after 5 hours. Similarly, low *FE* of H₂O₂ production (0.3 %) was obtained recently on BiVO₄ photoanode [9] and was ascribed to the fact that the photogenerated carriers predominantly do not engage in the two-electron pathway (eq. 5) for H₂O₂ formation but rather proceed *via* the four-electron pathway (eq. 6) to evolve O₂ even though from a thermodynamic point of view, both reactions are possible in the case of hematite as a photoanode (see Fig. S7).

4 Conclusions

The linear sweep voltammetry and long-term (5 hours) chronoamperometry experiments were carried out to determine the influence of various factors on the Faradaic efficiency of H₂O₂ generation *via* both oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) and water oxidation reaction (WOR). Hematite photoanode was combined with a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) with or without modification by incorporation of tin (II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) into the

hydrophilic part of GDE. The presence of hematite in the described system resulted in a significant shift of onset potential for ORR in a favourable direction about 400 mV and higher Faradaic efficiency compared with Pt. The SnPc modification of GDE caused a potential shift for ORR of around 100 mV.

The positive effect of 0.5 M phosphate buffer on H₂O₂ stability in the electrolyte was verified. The most successful was the combination of hematite photoanode and GDE with SnPc (0.5 M phosphate buffer as catholyte and air as inlet gas) as a cathode. The steady-state values (1 to 5 hours) of Faradaic efficiencies of H₂O₂ formation on GDE (around 50 %) were reached. For hematite, the Faradaic efficiency of H₂O₂ formation was only 0.4 % (even 1 M KHCO₃ and bubbling with CO₂ were used) showing that the reaction kinetics for H₂O₂ generation *via* WOR is not favourable.

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